

Analysis of Metalized 4H-SiC for High-Temperature Electric Weapon Applications

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ABSTRACT

While silicon (Si) based electronic materials and devices continue to play a dominant role in much of the electrical power industry, novel high-power and high-temperature materials are of great interest to the electric combat systems community. The technical interest in silicon carbide (SiC) is mainly due to its ability to operate at greatly elevated power and temperature ($>300^{\circ}\text{C}$) levels compared to its Si-based counterpart. High-power and temperature pulsed-power electronics can be exploited by future military combat systems, which could potentially provide significantly improved combat vehicle performance including increased lethality through extending the maximum obtainable gun performance using advanced electric weapon concepts such as electrothermal-chemical (ETC) and electromagnetic (EM) gun technologies.

The results of recent experiments conducted at the U.S. Army Research Laboratory (ARL) and the University of Delaware demonstrate the electrical behavior of SiC and metal ohmic-contact layers as a function of thermal stress. These experiments have determined that both titanium (Ti) and tantalum (Ta) metalization structures will provide a stable electrical ohmic-contact with n-type SiC at elevated temperatures for short bursts of time that are relevant for pulsed-powered electric weapon technologies. The Ti-SiC structure investigated exhibited a stable current-voltage (I-V) characteristic to as much as 800°C for a 10-min burst, while Ta metalizations provided a stable I-V characteristic on SiC even after a temperature burst of $1,000^{\circ}\text{C}$ for as long as a 3-min interval.

I. INTRODUCTION

Improved weapon performance can be quantified in terms of increased muzzle kinetic energy (KE), greater armor penetration, shorter projectile time of flight, or improved target accuracy. Advanced high-power electric weapon concepts such as electrothermal-chemical (ETC) or electromagnetic

(EM) gun systems, illustrated in Figure 1, have the demonstrated ability to improve the ballistic performance by as much as 30% over conventional guns with respect to projectile muzzle KE in ETC guns, or up to as much as 7 km/s muzzle velocity with EM railguns [1], [2].

Figure 1 ETC and EM Railgun Concepts

Other benefits of ETC gun technology include the ability to improve the ignition reproducibility by as much as a factor of 25–75 over large-caliber conventional chemical guns, which may have direct benefits toward lethality improvement due to increased target accuracy [3]. However, in order to fully provide the performance benefits offered by electric gun technologies, the integration of optimized high-power and high-temperature materials must be provided first. High-power materials will allow for improved reliability of pulsed-powered electric gun components or extend peak power capability, thereby minimizing the mass and volume of electric gun pulsed-power supplies. In addition, with the integration of optimized power electronics, the mobility of future combat systems can also be improved compared to current conventional combat vehicles due to reductions in system mass and volume as well as due to the improvements possible with electric vehicle propulsion and suspension technology that are presently under investigation.

To determine the feasibility of a SiC-metal contact operating at elevated temperatures for periods of

time relevant to electric weapon concepts, experiments have been carried out with single-crystalline, 4H (hexagonal crystal), n-type SiC. The SiC samples under study were obtained from Cree Research, Inc., and metal contacts were deposited by sputtering with metal layers, which followed by annealing at high temperatures for varying amounts of time. Resultant samples were characterized with a current-voltage (I-V) measurement technique to first test for an ohmic (nonrectifying) contact and also to characterize the thermal stability of the electrical properties at elevated temperature over varying lengths of time. The duration of high-temperature annealing was as long as 5 min, and all samples were annealed in an argon environment to avoid unwanted impurity contamination from oxygen or nitrogen into the metal-semiconductor layers. Ultimately, more detailed investigations incorporating x-ray diffraction (XRD) and transmission electron microscopy (TEM) can be performed to determine long-term effects of high temperatures on the characteristics of tested samples.

II. BENEFITS OF SiC IN ELECTRIC GUN MISSIONS

Significant advantages can be realized from high-temperature pulsed-power materials such as those necessary for electric combat systems. The main advantage of SiC for electric gun applications is in the ability to operate under high-current density and high-temperature conditions. The higher operating temperature in SiC is allowable due to the fact that the temperature at which thermally generated carriers in the bulk material exceed the dopant concentration is above 900° C, compared to 200° C for equivalently doped Si [4]. The overall system benefit with novel SiC power electrical systems is the reduction in mass and volume of pulsed-power components, which effectively increases the specific energy density of an electric gun pulsed-power system.

To illustrate the benefit of high-temperature capability, the results from calculations shown in Figure 2 provide an approximation of solid-state material mass required as a function of assumed operating current density. The calculations are based upon the simplified expression for total energy, Q , deposited to a given mass, m , having a known specific heat, C , for an allowed temperature rise, ΔT , as indicated in:

$$\Delta Q = mC\Delta T = \int P dt = \int I^2 R dt. \quad (1)$$

The resistance of the material for (1) is calculated from the simple resistivity expression for a semiconductor, which is:

$$\rho = \frac{1}{q\mu N_D}, \quad (2)$$

where q is the electronic charge, μ is the carrier mobility, and N_D is the dopant concentration. At a given current, as indicated in Figure 2, significant reductions in mass can be realized through the use of SiC due to its improved tolerance of higher temperature. The higher maximum intrinsic temperature (900° C for SiC vs. 200° C for Si) allows for increased maximum current density or reduced solid-state mass for a given current density. As indicated in Figure 2, SiC operating at 500° C and 700° C results in mass reductions of approximately 45% and 60%, respectively, compared to the conventional Si pulsed-power counter part, which is limited to a 180° C operational temperature.

Figure 2 Calculated Solid-State Material Mass as a Function of Current Density for a 3-ms Power Pulse and a Semiconductor Dopant Concentration of $1 \times 10^{14} \text{ cm}^{-3}$

Other electric gun applications of high-temperature materials include railgun contact materials or ETC plasma generator device components, which can also potentially provide improved weapon performance due to reduced rail erosion in EM guns or improved surface ablation properties for plasma generator components in ETC guns. With EM weapons systems, it is typical to achieve high current densities in rails and armatures, and in ETC guns high-temperature plasma sources that can produce detrimental effects to electrical conducting metallic components are generated. In recent tests conducted on EM rail material, for example, it has been demonstrated experimentally that a simulant aluminum armature on a Ti substrate produced the

best performance in terms of minimizing rail material deposition [5]. In addition, ETC gun plasma sources are known to operate in the 10–20,000 K temperature region, which can potentially lead to metal surface erosion and alterations to the low molecular weight plasma that is sought for ETC ignition and combustion control [6], [7]. It has been reported that a significant percentage (14–23%) of the total energy contained in the typical ETC plasma source is consumed by ablation and dissociation of polyethylene and copper components of ETC plasma generators [1]. In EM and ETC guns, the use of novel high-temperature materials such as metal-SiC structures can potentially lead to significant improvements to the lifetime or overall performance of future combat systems of interest to the Army.

III. EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE AND RESULTS

The experimental approach was to develop a feasibility analysis of various candidate high-temperature materials to determine the electrical performance as a function of elevated temperatures under burst conditions. The candidate materials were metal-SiC systems that are expected to perform reliably at elevated temperatures. A study of the literature on SiC systems for non-pulsed-power applications indicated that Ni, Ti, Ta, and W metals on SiC perform well with regard to specific contact resistance [8]. Ti and Ta are chosen here as metals for SiC due to their known high melting temperature (1,660° C and 2,990° C, respectively), demonstrated erosion properties (with Ti), and a history of quality ohmic contacts achieved with SiC substrates for other non-pulsed-powered applications [9], [10], [11].

IV. Ti-SiC I-V RESULTS

The results of the current-voltage (I-V) characteristics, obtained as illustrated by the simplified schematic diagram in Figure 3, of the Ti-SiC samples examined are given in Figures 4–6. The I-V characteristics are obtained by the measurement of the current flowing through the metalized sample as a function of the junction voltage applied across the sample. As shown in Figure 3, the current is monitored by an ammeter (Fluke 87) as a function of applied voltage, which is provided from a calibrated DC voltage generator (Datel 8500). Results from I-V Measurements of a Ti-SiC sample are shown in Figure 4.

Figure 3 Electrical (I-V) Characterization Arrangement for Metalized SiC Sample Materials

Figure 4 Ti-SiC Sample as Deposited and Annealed at 600° C for 5 min

Figure 5 Ti-SiC Sample as-Deposited and Annealed at 1,120° C for 2 min

The two I-V measurement curves shown are for a Ti-SiC sample "as-deposited" and after a 600° C anneal in forming gas (85% N₂, 15% H₂) for a burst of 5 min. As indicated by the measurements, the annealed sample displays a reduced slope, which reflects an overall increase in resistivity by about a factor of 2. The reason for the unexpected increased resistivity is not clear, but may be due to

Figure 6 Ti-SiC Sample I-V Characteristics for as-Deposited and Annealed Sample at 300, 600, 800, and 1,120° C

the relatively low annealing temperature used. A temperature of 600° C may not be high enough to form a desirable silicide phase at the metal semiconductor interface, which is generally known to reduce contact resistivity and provide a stable ohmic contact [12]. The second reason may be the nitrogen content of the forming gas that was used during the annealing to reduce the effects of oxygen. It is considered possible that a nitride phase was formed during the anneal that contributed to the degradation in contact quality as indicated by the increase in resistivity. Steps taken to alleviate this problem included increasing the initial anneal temperature to above 1,100° C, where Ti-SiC phases are known to form [13], and using argon as the ambient gas during all high-temperature steps to remove the possibility of nitride formation on the sample surfaces. The I-V results of a second Ti-SiC sample annealed at 1,120° C for 2 min in argon are shown in Figure 5, together with the "as-deposited" curve. Figure 5 shows that the Ti-SiC contact resistance decreased after annealing in argon, in contrast to the increasing resistance observed in Figure 4. It is believed that this important change is due to the substitution of argon forming gas, which prevented the formation of a nitride. Further high-temperature annealing was performed on the Ti-SiC sample having the I-V characteristics of Figure 5. Annealing was performed at 300, 600, and 800° C for a 5-min duration at each level, and an I-V measurement was performed at the completion of each anneal to determine the effect on the resistivity. Results from the three additional anneals of the Ti-SiC system, together with the I-V curves from the as-deposited and the 1,120° C initial annealing step, are given in the plots of Figure 6.

V. Ta-SiC I-V RESULTS

Similar high-temperature annealing experiments were conducted with Ta metalization layers on equivalent SiC substrates used as Ti-SiC experiments. The resulting I-V curves are given in Figures 7-9. An outstanding feature of the Ta metalization on SiC was revealed by the I-V curve for the as-deposited sample as shown in Figure 7. It is noted that the as-deposited Ta layer produces a rectifying (Schottky barrier) contact. The rectifying behavior is indicated by the exponential relationship observed in the I-V measurement of the Ta-SiC sample. However, an ohmic contact was achieved in the Ta-SiC system after an anneal cycle of 1,120° C for 3 min as indicated by the I-V curve of Figure 8.

Figure 7 Current-Voltage Characteristic for Ta-SiC as-Deposited Sample

Figure 8 Current-Voltage Characteristic for Ta-SiC Sample Annealed at 1,120° C for 3 min

Additional testing was performed with the Ta-SiC prototype sample at elevated temperatures of 600 and 1,000° C for varying burst lengths. The I-V results of these experiments are given in Figure 9, which indicate a stable I-V and, therefore, stable ohmic contact structure under all temperature conditions investigated.

Figure 9 Current-Voltage Characteristic for Ta-SiC Sample Annealed at 600, 1,000, and 1,120° C

VI. CONCLUSIONS

Based upon the results from the I-V measurements obtained for the titanium and tantalum metalization layers on the n-type SiC substrate employed in the experiments, it has been determined that both metals offer a reliable and stable electrical contact to n-type 4H SiC for elevated temperature operation. The complete temperature ranges considered for the Ti and Ta systems were 300–1,120° C and 600–1,120° C, respectively, and the temperature burst duration ranged from 2–5 min. The standard deviation calculated from the I-V measurements taken on the Ti-SiC system at the high-temperature bursts gives a value of a 0.167 ohms for an average sample resistivity of 4.45 ohms. This value of standard deviation represents approximately 3.8% of the average value of sample resistivity. The Ta-SiC system investigated through I-V measurements produced an even smaller standard deviation of only 0.05 ohms for a sample having an average resistivity of 4.25 ohms, which represents approximately 1.2% of the average sample resistivity.

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